

ECONOMIC REVIEW OF THE STATE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS IN TAJIKISTAN

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Abstract

Currently, the "Green Economy Development Strategy for 2023-2037" has been adopted in the Republic of Tajikistan. This important document defines the tasks, goals and prospects of the country's strategic indicators. The main purpose of this document is, first of all, internal implementation, as well as implementation and proposal of independent cooperation with international financial structures, development partners.

Keywords: Water for Sustainable Development, Renewable Energy, Energy, Tajikistan.

In this year's message of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan to the Majlisi Oli, which presented the main political and economic processes of Tajikistan, annual GDP growth of up to 8.0% was projected, along with other tasks, it was also stated that "... the implementation of the "green economy", rapid industrialization, the use of innovative technologies..."(1) from the main processes in the development, stability and improvement of the quality of the national economy, and above all in terms of the rapid industrialization of the country, which has been declared as the "Years of Industrial Development" in 2022-2026, has its own special position should occupy. It is worth noting that, according to statistical data, at the end of 2021, the share of industrial products in the total of domestic products at current prices was 20.2%, and construction was 9.01%.

The energy sector of Tajikistan occupies a special position in the implementation of the fourth national goal of the country - the process of rapid industrialization, taking into account the current initiative - the International Decade of Action for 2018-2028 "Water for Sustainable Development", because in the past years 287 small and large hydropower plants, 1.5 thousand kilometers of high-voltage transmission lines, 50 high-voltage substations were built and renovated, and in total 75% of the country's energy infrastructure was renovated, which provided the opportunity to build more than 2000 megawatts of additional energy capacity (1).

Currently, international financial partners consider the special indicators of "green economy", "green energy" and other indicators of environmental health and nature as one of the key indicators and put them in the first place when developing investment projects. Usually, in recent years, the economy has been evaluated taking into account the improvement of nature protection, environmental disinfection, sources of restoration, etc., and these indicators are considered as a modern economic trend.

International experience has shown that in recent years, due to road closures, current sanctions, the epidemic of Covid-19, etc., it is possible to promote production in many production plants of global companies that, according to their current plans, taking into account the concluded contracts, have satisfied their production requirements. could not, and this brought the need for more supply from internal sources and placed it in the first place in terms of topicality.

In 2020, the International Energy Agency considered the production of more than 30.0% (3) of the energy produced by the European Union countries from renewable energy sources, and according to the indicators of the annual report of the United Nations Environment Program, in 2020 compared to 2019, there was an increase noted that global energy from renewable sources (RES) is 2.6 times greater than the increase in production of fossil fuels (3).

According to the data published by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), 72% of the total energy consumption in 2020 will be new sources of water, wind, solar, geothermal and bioenergy (4).

During this period, especially the economies of countries that do not have renewable energy sources and whose economies are more dependent on the fulfillment of contractual requirements for the supply of energy-exhausting materials suffered the most, and their economic indicators decreased negatively.

Tajikistan, as a full-fledged member of the international economy, should improve and develop its economic strategy in the future, taking into account such indicators. Because the Republic of Tajikistan has a special and good position in terms of water, solar and wind resources, i.e. renewable sources of energy production due to the aforementioned existing resources. Moreover, the practical experience of the world economy in recent years clearly shows that in the current conditions of the global economic crisis, the current sanctions, the demand for common energy resources such as oil and gas products, coal, etc. are decreasing day by day.

To compare the ratio of electricity production from existing sources, on a global scale, if we make a conclusion, we must admit that the Republic of Tajikistan occupies one of the first places in the system of renewable sources. According to the published data of the Ministry of Energy and Water of Tajikistan, the share of electricity produced from "green energy" sources in our Republic is 95.0% (5). Now that this indicator on the scale of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) in the balance of the production of the share of electricity generated from "green energy" sources in 2020 was only 19.6%, and in comparison with the year 2000 it was only 1. It has increased by 7 percentage points (6).

At the same time, the process of electricity production, according to the program "Global Energy

Trends - 2021 Edition" (7), the share of electricity produced by water sources in the global energy balance has remained stable since 2000. in the range of approximately 16.0% to 18.0% in the total share of production, the share of electricity from renewable sources, primarily from wind and solar energy, has increased by more than 6% (7).

Such a process of progress or self-jumping of electricity production due to renewable sources made it possible for the share of such energy in the energy balance of the European Union to reach 39.0% by the end of 2020, the People's Republic of China to 28.0%, the Republic of India to 23. 0% and in the Russian Federation up to 20.0% (7).

According to the available data, in 2022 the population of Tajikistan will amount to 10.0 million, and according to the data published by the Ministry of Energy and Water of the Republic, approximately 10.0% of the population of the Republic suffers from a lack of access to sources of electricity supply, and more are rural. That is, taking into account such data, it is possible to conclude that up to 0.6 million of the population living in areas without access to electricity. (in some sources up to 1.0 million people) can be direct customers of renewable energy producers.

From the point of view of the effectiveness of saving costs and obtaining positive operating results, the received income should at least cover the spent costs. Therefore, taking into account the geography and composition of the population in the Republic, carrying high-voltage lines to the power supply points in the mountainous areas requires a lot of expenses and cannot meet the basics of self-sufficiency. It is precisely because of the requirements of the economy of costs that the need and demand for the construction of renewable sources of electricity, due to the sun and wind, is the current demand for the satisfaction of the population of these regions.

It is not hidden that activities in certain production areas require the existence of legal grounds and supporting factors. In order to promote work activities on the construction and operation of power plants producing energy from sunlight, wind power, geothermal water, biological waste (biomass) and rivers and the procedure for its use, the Law of the Republic of Tajikistan

"On the use of renewable energy sources" No. 587, dated 12.01.s. .2010 adopted.

This law stipulates the procedure for the production and consumption of the produced energy to ensure its activity and its sale through the energy network of the Republic. It follows that both real and legal entities can have such production activity.

According to the provisions of this law, energy production plants from renewable sources are included in the small energy group as - micro, mini and small power plants with a capacity of up to 100 kW, from 101 to 1000 kW and from 1001 to 30000 kW (6). At present, the experience of the operation of such power plants shows that only solar and wind power are used in the Republic, and geothermal water reserves, biological waste (biomass) and small rivers are hardly used. In this regard, taking into account the implementation of legislative requirements, in the near future, in our opinion, it is possible to implement business activities.

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